

Interview Guide: The Patient

This guide will be used to interview patients following the visit for contraceptive counseling in which the decision aid was provided to the patient to work through and bring to the visit. The provider also had access to the decision aid prior to the visit.

Notes for the research assistant: Introduce yourself and your role in the study to the interviewee. Provide information about yourself so that the interviewee understands how your background may or may not be relevant to the interview.

For each of the following questions, use the numbered questions to guide the interview and use the bulleted questions as probes if needed. Once each of the bulleted points has been addressed (either because interviewee offered it up or you have asked the probe), move on to the next numbered question. If an interviewee answers one of the numbered questions while answering another numbered question, there is no need to repeat the question.

Please record the interview and ensure that voices can be clearly heard on the recording.

Thank you again for participating in the study. My name is [X], and I am a research associate on the study. This next part of the study will be a 15-20 minute interview. During the interview I will ask you some open ended questions about the contraceptive application itself, how the app impacted your conversation with your provider, and some questions that are specific to being a servicemember in relation to the study. Just as a reminder we will be recording the interview, and I am going to start recording now...

Section 1

Let's begin with some questions about the use of the app in your discussion of contraceptive options.

1. Approximately how much time in total did you spend using the app before the appointment?

2. Your preferences about your birth control method have to do with your personal choice about your method. In what ways, if any, did the app impact your ability to identify and communicate your preferences to your provider?

This question addresses the patient's perceived ability to identify and communicate preferences.

3. Your values have to do with the amount of weight you place on a particular characteristic of a contraceptive method. Did you feel empowered to talk about your own values with your provider?

This question addresses the patient's perceived ability to identify and communicate preferences.

If yes, in what ways, if any, did the app contribute to you feeling empowered to talk about your preferences or your values?

This question addresses the patient's comfort in communicating with the provider.

4. Do you feel that you and your provider made a shared decision about your birth control choice? Why or why not?

5. How comfortable are you with your decision about your birth control choice?

These questions get at the patient's perception of the shared decision-making process and therefore addresses the perceived effectiveness of the tool in enhancing shared decision making.

6. Do you feel that you had an important role in the decision about your birth control method?

This question gets at the patient's feelings about having agency in the decision-making process and therefore addresses the effectiveness of the tool in enhancing patient agency.

Section 2 (check time)

Thank you, now let's move onto some questions more specific to being a servicemember in relation to the study.

7. First, which Service are you in?

8. Second, in which of the following categories for your rank do you fall:

E1-E3

E4-E6

E7-E9

O1-O3

O4-O9

Warrant Officer W1-W5

9. What, if any, military-relevant concerns or issues influenced your contraceptive choice?

- **For example, did you have any concerns related to a contraceptive option that were related to your assigned duties in the military?**

This question gets at actually identifying whether or not the patient identified and/or expressed military-relevant patient values.

10. In some health situations you may have several options for care. For example, perhaps you could choose one therapy or another therapy. As a service member, how much input do you feel you generally have in making decisions in these types of situations?

- **Think about the last time you had to make a medical decision. Did you feel empowered to make the decision?**
- **Can you think of a health situation when you felt as though you did not have a say in the decision, but felt like you should? Tell me about it.**

This question gets at the patient's feelings about having a say in preference-sensitive decisions.

11. This app was meant to help you and your provider with shared decision making around a medical decision. Would you like to use an app like this (or another such tool) in the future for other medical decisions? Why or why not?

If yes, For what types of decisions do you think it would be most valuable to you?

This open-ended question provides the interviewee an opportunity to share any additional thoughts about their interest in participating in shared decision making in the future.